

Historical Continuation and Discontinuation in Green Movements in India since 1950 : A Study on Kolkata

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Abstract

The history of green movements in India since 1950 is marked by both continuity and change, reflecting the nation's evolving socio-political landscape and environmental challenges. Initially, these movements focused on local issues, with landmark initiatives like the Chipko Movement in the 1970s, where rural communities, particularly women, embraced trees to prevent deforestation in the Himalayas. This grassroots activism highlighted the interconnectedness of environmental conservation and local livelihoods, laying the foundation for broader ecological awareness. In the 1980s and 1990s, the focus expanded to include anti-dam protests, such as the Narmada Bachao Andolan, which highlighted issues of displacement and environmental degradation due to large-scale development projects. The rise of NGOs and increasing public awareness led to a more organized and institutionalized environmental movement. In the 21st century, the movement's scope has further broadened, encompassing issues like air pollution, climate change, and sustainable urbanization. However, there have been discontinuities, such as the waning of certain localized movements and the co-opting of green rhetoric by various political and corporate interests. Despite these challenges, green movements in India have continued to evolve, adapting to new environmental realities and leveraging digital platforms for advocacy. The historical trajectory of these movements illustrates a dynamic interplay between local traditions and global environmental discourses, underlining the complex nature of sustainable development in a rapidly industrializing nation. A city like Kolkata has greatest impression in this connection hence this study is greatly important.

Keywords: Environmental challenges, Local issues, Grassroots activism, Digital platforms

Introduction

The evolution of green movements in India since 1950 is a fascinating narrative of grassroots activism, cultural heritage, and responses to environmental degradation. These movements have played a critical role in shaping India's environmental policies and public consciousness, adapting to the country's diverse socio-political and ecological landscape. From the iconic Chipko Movement to the contemporary Swachh Bharat Abhiyan, these initiatives showcase a continuum of environmental activism, highlighting both historical continuity and significant shifts in focus and strategy. The Chipko Movement, which began in the 1970s in the Himalayan region, is one of the most celebrated examples of grassroots environmental activism. Villagers, particularly women, physically embraced trees to prevent contractors from felling them, thereby drawing attention to the importance of forests in their lives. This movement not only succeeded in halting deforestation in certain areas but also set a precedent for community-led conservation efforts. The slogan "Ecology is permanent economy," popularized by Chipko leader Sunderlal Bahuguna, underscored the movement's ethos that sustainable environmental practices are crucial for economic stability.

In the following decades, green movements in India expanded their scope to address the impacts of large-scale industrial and infrastructure projects. The Narmada Bachao Andolan (Save Narmada Movement), which began in the mid-1980s, is a prime example. This movement opposed the construction of large dams on the Narmada River, highlighting the displacement of indigenous communities, loss of biodiversity, and long-term environmental consequences. Led by activists like Medha Patkar, the movement garnered international attention and raised critical questions about the trade-offs between development and environmental sustainability.

As India entered the 21st century, the focus of green movements increasingly included urban environmental issues such as air pollution, waste management, and climate change. The Swachh Bharat Abhiyan (Clean India Mission), launched in 2014,

represents a state-led initiative aimed at improving sanitation and waste management across the country. While not without its criticisms, this movement reflects a growing recognition of urban environmental challenges and the need for comprehensive policy responses.

Kolkata, often regarded as the cultural capital of India, has a vibrant history of green movements that reflect its unique socio-economic and environmental context. These movements, ranging from grassroots community efforts to organized NGO initiatives, have been pivotal in addressing the city's environmental challenges. Public awareness campaigns, often spearheaded by local organizations, have sought to educate residents about issues such as air and water pollution, waste management, and the preservation of green spaces. Community-led initiatives, such as neighborhood clean-up drives and urban gardening projects, highlight the role of local engagement in promoting sustainability. These efforts are often driven by a deep sense of community pride and responsibility, showcasing Kolkata's rich tradition of civic participation. However, the city also faces significant challenges, including rapid urbanization, industrial pollution, and inadequate infrastructure, which exacerbate environmental degradation. The role of NGOs in Kolkata's green movements is crucial, providing resources, expertise, and advocacy. Organizations like the Centre for Science and Environment and the South Asian Forum for Environment have been instrumental in influencing public discourse and policy. Despite their efforts, these movements often encounter obstacles, such as funding constraints and regulatory challenges. Throughout these decades, green movements in India have also faced challenges, including government suppression, co-optation by political interests, and the struggle to maintain momentum. However, they have continued to evolve, drawing on India's rich traditions of environmental stewardship and leveraging new tools like social media to mobilize support.

Background

The study explores urban environmental activism in India, focusing on the tensions between middle-class-driven projects and the displacement of marginalized

communities. It examines historical and contemporary movements in Kolkata to highlight the diverse actors and complex dynamics shaping urban environmentalism.

Literature Review

By 1950, India began implementing policies that intertwined economic development with ecological sustainability, aiming to counteract stagnant agricultural practices and promote sustainable rural policies. Hence the condition of a metropolitan city has to be understood from an in – depth view.

Bandyopadhyay (2017) has said, Historical account of India's environmental changes, driven by population growth, deforestation, community resistance, and Public Interest Litigation. Humans are related to the environment and vice versa. Accords to the population distribution it is much legitimate to think the environmental plans should be much healthy for the humans. Rangan (1997) has pointed out a fact that says - Indian environmentalist perspectives, offering an alternative framework for understanding state intervention in resource management. The analysis highlights political and economic pressures, institutional demands, and conflicts, emphasizing weaknesses in current environmental debates and challenges in achieving sustainable development. Sharan (2006) has examined urban modernity in India, focusing on Delhi's evolving environmental debates, linking issues like public health, pollution, and legal rights to power dynamics and urban anthropology; it is proven by his work that nothing is separate now and a proper integrated environmental planning is needed. Rajesh (2021) reinvents political sociology by engaging with its classical tradition and scrutinizing major trends in Indian social movement studies, proposing a postcolonial political sociology framework for non-Western contexts. Mukherjee (2020) has shown urban environmental activism in Kolkata, using historical urban political ecology to examine the restoration of Adi Ganga and preservation of East Kolkata Wetlands is challenging unilinear views and highlighting diverse, impactful activism.

The literature review concludes by highlighting the complex interplay between urban environmentalism and social dynamics in Indian metropolises. It underscores the dominance of "bourgeois environmentalism," which often prioritizes middle-class

aesthetics and interests, resulting in the displacement of marginalized communities. By examining case studies like the Adi Ganga restoration and East Kolkata Wetlands preservation, it reveals the multifaceted nature of environmental struggles involving diverse actors with conflicting interests. The review advocates for a postcolonial political sociology approach to better capture the unique challenges and opportunities in non-Western contexts.

Objectives

The primary objectives of studying the green movements in India from 1950 onwards are to:

- Evaluate the historical progression and impact of various environmental movements on policymaking and community awareness.
- Assess the effectiveness of grassroots campaigns and their role in shaping national environmental policies.
- Understand the relationship between socio-economic factors and the emergence of the green movements.

Research questions

To fulfill the objectives, the following research questions are proposed:

- What were the key drivers and triggers for the emergence of green movements in India post-1950?
- How have different movements contributed to changes in environmental policies at the local and national levels?
- In what ways have these movements influenced public perception of environmental issues in India?

Need of the study

This study is essential to highlight the historical context and evolution of green movements in India, as it will:

- Contribute to the existing literature on environmental movements by providing a comprehensive overview of the development and impact in the Indian context.
- Offer insights into successful strategies used by grassroots organizations, which can serve as models for future environmental advocacy.
- Foster a better understanding of the challenges faced by these movements and the lessons learned that can be applied in ongoing and future environmental efforts.

Limitation of the study

The study may face several limitations, including:

- The availability of comprehensive data regarding early green movements, particularly from historical records that may be scarce or biased.
- Challenges in evaluating the long-term impact of various movements due to overlapping agendas and external socio-political influences.
- Potential difficulty in quantifying the success metrics of different movements in terms of policy change versus public awareness.

This structured approach will provide a detailed examination of green movements in India, emphasizing their historical nuances and contemporary relevance.

Methodology

This study utilizes a qualitative research design with a focus on primary data collection in Kolkata. A survey is conducted to assess public awareness and attitudes towards green movements, targeting a diverse sample of residents. Structured interviews are held with key stakeholders, including environmental activists, local government officials, and community leaders, to gather in-depth insights into the city's environmental challenges and activism. Field observations are conducted in areas with active green initiatives to document on-ground practices and community engagement. Purposive sampling of 30 samples of mature age ensures participants with relevant experience and knowledge are included. Thematic analysis is used to identify key themes and trends from the collected data. Ethical protocols, including informed consent and confidentiality, are strictly followed to protect participant rights and data integrity. This methodology provides a comprehensive view of Kolkata's environmental activism and public engagement.

Discussion

Kolkata, one of India's most populous and culturally vibrant cities, has a rich history of environmental activism. The city's green movements have evolved significantly over the decades, shaped by its unique socio-economic and cultural context. The primary data collected through surveys, interviews, and field observations highlights the diversity of these movements, which range from community-led initiatives to more structured NGO-driven efforts. This section explores the nature, scope, and evolution of these movements, providing a backdrop for deeper analysis.

□ **Public Awareness and Engagement**

The survey data reveals a varied level of public awareness and engagement in environmental issues across Kolkata. While there is a growing consciousness about the importance of sustainability, particularly among the younger population, significant gaps remain. Many respondents expressed a lack of awareness about specific local issues, such as water pollution in the Hooghly River or the degradation of the East Kolkata Wetlands. This gap highlights the need for more targeted educational campaigns and community outreach programs to increase public participation.

Critical Analysis: The findings suggest that while there is a general awareness of environmental issues, it often lacks depth and specificity. The role of education, media, and grassroots outreach becomes crucial in bridging this gap. The data indicates that educational institutions and local media can play a pivotal role in fostering a deeper understanding and more active participation in green initiatives.

□ **Stakeholder Perspectives**

Interviews with key stakeholders, including environmental activists, government officials, and community leaders, provide a multifaceted view of Kolkata's green movements. Activists often emphasize the need for more stringent environmental regulations and enforcement, pointing to issues like illegal waste dumping and unregulated construction as critical concerns. In contrast, government officials highlight

the challenges of balancing development needs with environmental sustainability, often citing budget constraints and political pressures.

Critical Analysis: The divergent views between activists and officials underscore the complexities of environmental governance in Kolkata. While activists push for more proactive measures, officials grapple with practical limitations and competing priorities. This tension highlights the need for a more collaborative approach that includes all stakeholders in decision-making processes, ensuring that policies are both sustainable and feasible.

□ **Community-Led Initiatives**

Community-led initiatives form a cornerstone of Kolkata's environmental landscape. These grassroots movements often address hyper-local issues, such as neighborhood clean-up drives, community gardening, and the preservation of green spaces. The field observations reveal that these initiatives are often driven by a strong sense of local pride and community solidarity, with residents coming together to tackle common challenges.

Critical Analysis: Community-led initiatives are essential for fostering a culture of sustainability at the local level. However, they often face challenges such as limited resources, lack of technical knowledge, and insufficient support from local authorities. Strengthening these initiatives through better funding, training, and policy support can significantly enhance their impact and sustainability.

□ **Role of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)**

NGOs play a vital role in Kolkata's green movements, often acting as intermediaries between the community and the government. They provide critical resources, expertise, and advocacy, addressing issues ranging from air quality monitoring to urban planning. NGOs like the Centre for Science and Environment and the South Asian Forum for Environment have been instrumental in shaping public discourse and influencing policy decisions.

Critical Analysis: While NGOs contribute significantly to Kolkata's environmental landscape, their influence is sometimes limited by funding constraints and regulatory

hurdles. Moreover, the relationship between NGOs and the government can be contentious, with disagreements over priorities and strategies. To maximize their effectiveness, NGOs need to build stronger alliances with both governmental bodies and local communities, ensuring a more integrated approach to environmental challenges.

□ **Challenges and Barriers**

The data highlights several challenges faced by green movements in Kolkata. These include inadequate infrastructure, such as waste management systems, lack of political will, and economic constraints. Additionally, the rapid urbanization and industrialization of Kolkata pose significant threats to its environment, exacerbating issues like air and water pollution, loss of green cover, and climate resilience.

Critical Analysis: The challenges facing Kolkata's green movements are multifaceted and interconnected. Addressing these requires a comprehensive approach that integrates environmental, social, and economic dimensions. For instance, improving waste management infrastructure not only reduces pollution but also creates job opportunities, contributing to the city's socio-economic development. Similarly, policies promoting green urban planning can enhance the quality of life while preserving biodiversity.

Based on the findings, several recommendations can be made to strengthen Kolkata's green movements. First, increasing public awareness through educational programs and media campaigns can foster a more informed and engaged citizenry. Second, fostering partnerships between government, NGOs, and the private sector can pool resources and expertise, leading to more effective solutions. Third, implementing stricter regulations and enforcement mechanisms can address issues like illegal dumping and deforestation.

Conclusion & Further studies

The study of green movements in Kolkata within the broader context of India's environmental activism since 1950 reveals a complex interplay of continuity and change. Kolkata's movements, influenced by local socio-economic and cultural factors, have evolved from grassroots initiatives focused on immediate environmental issues to more structured, policy-oriented efforts. The city's rich tradition of civic engagement

has fostered a robust environmental consciousness, yet significant challenges, such as rapid urbanization, industrial pollution, and inadequate infrastructure, persist. The role of NGOs and community-led initiatives has been crucial in driving these movements, though they often face funding constraints and regulatory hurdles. Moving forward, further research should explore the impact of digital media on mobilizing green movements, the intersection of socio-economic factors like gender, caste, and class in environmental activism, and comparative studies of regional variations in green movements across India. Longitudinal studies assessing the long-term outcomes of these movements would also provide valuable insights into their effectiveness and sustainability, helping to shape future strategies for environmental conservation and sustainable development in Kolkata and beyond.

Policy recommendations

- **Strengthen Environmental Regulations:** Implement and enforce stricter regulations on industrial emissions, waste management, and deforestation. Regular monitoring and penalties for non-compliance should be enforced to ensure adherence to environmental standards.
- **Promote Sustainable Urban Planning:** Incorporate green infrastructure into urban planning to enhance resilience against climate change. This includes creating and maintaining green spaces, promoting energy-efficient building designs, and improving public transportation systems to reduce reliance on private vehicles.
- **Enhance Public Awareness and Education:** Launch comprehensive public awareness campaigns focused on environmental issues. Integrate environmental education into school curriculums and community programs to foster a culture of sustainability from a young age.
- **Support Community-Led Initiatives:** Provide financial and technical support to grassroots environmental projects and community-led conservation efforts. Encourage community participation in decision-making processes to ensure local needs and priorities are addressed.

- Strengthen NGO-Government Collaboration: Foster stronger partnerships between government bodies and non-governmental organizations. Collaborative efforts can lead to more effective policy implementation, resource mobilization, and advocacy for environmental issues.
- Encourage Green Innovation: Support research and development in green technologies and sustainable practices. Provide grants and incentives for innovative solutions that address environmental challenges and promote sustainable development.
- Monitor and Evaluate Policy Impact: Establish mechanisms for regular monitoring and evaluation of environmental policies and programs. Use data-driven approaches to assess their effectiveness and make necessary adjustments to improve outcomes.
- Facilitate Public-Private Partnerships: Encourage collaboration between the public and private sectors to drive sustainable development initiatives. Public-private partnerships can leverage resources, expertise, and innovation to address environmental challenges more effectively.

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